

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Advanced Manufacturing Research Centre (AMRC)

Data augmentation and synthetic
data generation for low frequency
and sparse data problems

5-16 December 2022

Contents

1	Executive summary	2
1.1	Challenge overview	2
1.2	Data overview	2
1.3	Main objectives	3
1.4	Approach	3
1.5	Main conclusions	5
1.6	Limitations	5
1.7	Recommendations and future work	6
2	Data overview	7
2.1	Forging data	7
2.2	Machining data	8
2.3	Workpiece data	9
2.4	Data quality issues	10
3	Data exploration and visualisation	10
3.1	Influence of forging temperature regime	10
3.2	Tool wearing decreases sequentially	11
4	Statistical modelling	11
4.1	Feature extraction	13
4.2	Quality metrics	15
4.3	Model Inference Results	21
5	Data augmentation	27
5.1	Dimensionality reduction with PCA	28
5.2	SDV library	28
5.3	MAE method	31
6	Future work and research avenues	34
7	Team members	35

1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

The Advanced Manufacturing Research Centre (AMRC) group is part of the UK's High Value Manufacturing (HVM) Catapult, whose mission is to accelerate the concepts-to-commercial-reality process and create a sustainable future for high-value manufacturing.

Many manufacturers rely on the manufacture of a small number of high-value workpieces. In contrast to high-volume production, any workpieces rejected in high-value manufacturing represent a large individual investment of resources. Nonetheless, the reasons for rejection are often difficult to determine, which hinders the improvement of the manufacturing process.

The reason for this difficulty is the lack of data available on the manufactured workpiece - due to it undergoing several processes, the scarcity of data collected, and the limited sample size in low-volume, high-value manufacturing. Early prediction of workpiece failure would increase productivity and reduce waste by an early stop of the manufacturing process.

The workpieces of interest for this Data Study Group are high-value, low-yield ones since they are either made from expensive materials or undergo expensive treatments. Thus, any improvements that lead to fewer rejected pieces will be of high business value and save resources.

AMRC has recently collected data on 16 such products, from their forging through machining to their final quality check. This challenge aims to explore the potential of this novel dataset for high-value, low-yield research with a particular emphasis on failure prediction, data augmentation, and data viability.

1.2 Data overview

Here we give a bird's eye-view of the data, a more detailed description will be presented in the next section.

The dataset is composed of multiple subsets, which can further be grouped into three categories:

- The first is the forging data, describing the production and environment parameters during the forging process.
- The second is the machining data, describing the production and environment parameters during the machining process.
- The third is various descriptive measurements on the quality of the workpiece, either during the process or after.

The forging and machining data consist of high-frequency time series of values drawn from sensors attached to the production tools, whereas the data types of the third category are more versatile, also including quality measurements (e.g. surface roughness) and three-dimensional scans of the object.

All these datasets describe 16 workpieces during their entire processing lifespan. Among these 16 workpieces, eight workpieces were forged under a markedly higher temperature regime than the others.

1.3 Main objectives

The overall aim of this project is to explore the potential of the AMRC high-value manufacturing dataset. Specifically, we aim to answer the following questions:

- Can we predict workpiece failure with a limited sample of data?
- Can we augment the original data to train more accurate models?
- Which features are the most valuable for failure prediction?
- Can we improve the data collection process, say, by lowering the cost?

1.4 Approach

According to each person's research interests, we divided ourselves into two teams. One team studied the relationship between various production parameters and the workpiece quality via statistical models (SM), and the other team focused on data augmentation (DA).

The SM team first extracted representative features from the forging and machining time series. Then, they used skewed normal distributions and gamma distributions to quantify the workpiece quality: measurements closer to the target value represent higher quality. Finally, they built a machine learning model using the XGBoost framework to predict output quality via the forging and machining time series features.

This team also applied interpretable machine learning methods in an effort to produce explanations for the most important criteria in determining output quality. In particular, they used SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) [6] to determine the critical features which influenced the outcome.

In order to provide a decision-making framework to optimise data collection methods in deployment, they took the cost into consideration. They built a dendrogram illustrating the correlation of various features. If one feature with a high SHAP value (i.e., an important feature) is costly to collect, the manufacturer can look through the dendrogram and find potentially lower-cost substitutes.

While the SM team was building statistical models, the DA team proposed a method to generate synthetic forging data. The major difficulty they faced was the limited sample size, stemming from the key issue of limited production runs for parts. Although the provided long time series can be segmented into many shorter ones to yield more training samples, the synthetic time series generated from these will be also be short.

To overcome this difficulty, they borrowed an idea from the Masked AutoEncoder [4]. The idea of Masked AutoEncoder is to build an asymmetric encoder-decoder pair, where a data point (e.g. an image) is masked randomly at several locations. The encoder transforms the unmasked parts into an embedding, and the decoder transforms the embedding back into the whole data point. Since there are many different ways to mask a data point, one can generate many potential training samples.

Once such a masked autoencoder is built, one can add noise to an existing embedding and then use the already trained decoder to generate the corresponding time series to produce synthetic examples. The generated time series can be attributed to the same workpiece and thus

share the same quality outcome. Increasing the training dataset in this way is likely to retain statistical similarity with the input dataset, while introducing a quantifiable level of uncertainty related to the level of noise added to the input embedding.

1.5 Main conclusions

The experiments carried out during this challenge led to the following contributions:

- During quality inference the XGBoost model performed well in predicting the final quality despite the low number of samples.
- In addition, the model trained on forging data alone yielded equally good results.
- The proposed data augmentation method yielded different results on subsets of the data. For the workpieces produced at a lower temperature, the generated time series resembled the original dataset well. For the pieces produced at a higher temperature, the generated time series did not resemble the original ones at all.

1.6 Limitations

Although the models trained for quality prediction fit well on both the training set and the test set, we are unable to predict the level of generalisability of these results to either a production setting or to other parts produced in similar settings. This is due to the extremely limited sample size bounding the model's robustness, and potentially introducing unforeseen bias stemming from the data collection process.

Model performance is also difficult to contextualise without empirical validation. While XGBoost may be considered a generally acceptable choice of model for problem sets where sample size is an issue, it may be that alternate choices of model may yield superior results.

Due to time limits, we did not manage to combine the results of the two teams together. Introducing data augmentation into the training process for the machine learning model could be expected to produce more robust results, or reduce the potential for collection bias to influence the results through the suppression of outliers in the dataset.

1.7 Recommendations and future work

In terms of solutions to the original problem of limited sample sizes for input data, we suggest that integration of synthetic data augmentation as previously mentioned could be a productive way to produce more robust and generalisable models. However, this practice may also reduce the performance or fitness of the model to the particular dataset in question, and further experimentation would be required to evaluate the factors influencing this tendency.

We would also suggest assessing the feature importance work conducted during this challenge, and determining whether concentrating additional resources on producing higher-frequency or more sensitive measurements of the more highly ranked features in terms of importance could have a positive impact on model performance. In addition, it would be interesting to replicate some related research papers [8], in which the researchers similarly use Shapley values as part of a decision-making model for targeting process improvements.

2 Data overview

The dataset is composed of multiple subsets, which can further be grouped into three categories:

- The first is the forging data, describing the production and environment parameters during the forging process.
- The second is the machining data, describing the production and environment parameters during the machining process.
- The third is various descriptive measurements on the quality of the workpiece, either during the process or after.

The forging and machining data consist of high-frequency time series of values drawn from sensors attached to the production tools, whereas the data types of the third category are more versatile, also including quality measurements (e.g. surface roughness) and three-dimensional scans of the object. The data collection sources are represented in Figure 1. Individual sensor sources will be addressed in detail in the following sections.

All these datasets describe 16 workpieces during their entire processing lifespan. Among these 16 workpieces, eight workpieces were forged under a markedly higher temperature regime than the others.

2.1 Forging data

The forging data set is a multi-dimensional time series describing 101 aspects of the forging process. The forging of each part took about 10 minutes. The sampling frequency is 100Hz (i.e., 1 data point per 10ms), and thus the number of data points per time series is approximately 60,000.

These 16 pieces underwent two different heat treatments. Among them, eight workpieces (9-16) were forged under a significantly higher temperature than the other eight (1-8).

Figure 1: Relation between the various datasets. Each green item represents a collection of sensor data.

2.2 Machining data

The machining data is comprised of three subsets: spike, edge, and tooling, each representing a step of the machining process. A significant portion of data is missing here.

The **spike** dataset is a high-frequency multi-dimensional time series sampled at 2.5kHz. It describes the following production parameters:

- Tension
- Torsion
- Bending moment X
- Bending moment Y
- Temperature

The spike data corresponding to the pieces numbered 03, 07, 08, 10, and 16 are missing. The data corresponding to the subprocess numbered 030 is also missing.

The **edge** dataset was collected at the same time as the spike dataset, but with a slightly lower frequency of 333Hz.

The **tooling** dataset contains pre-cut wear and post-cut wear metrics.

2.3 Workpiece data

While the above two datasets describe the production parameters, the workpiece datasets describe intrinsic attributes of the workpieces which measure the quality of the process outcome. Multiple datasets are present here, each describing a different aspect (e.g., surface, interior) of the workpiece.

The **GOM (scan)** dataset shows the 3D model of the workpiece after forging. It can identify, inside the workpiece, potential cracks which can lead to workpiece rejection. These measurements are provided as stereolithography (.STL) files, which describe the surface topography of a three-dimensional object as a collection of triangular planes.

The **XRD** dataset shows the *X-ray diffraction analysis* results of the workpiece, either after forging or after machining. They measure various aspects of crystallographic structure of the workpieces, such as full half width at maximum (FHWM).

The **CMM** dataset describes the workpiece geometry after machining. Each metric is a 3-tuple in the form of (target value, tolerance range, actual value). Three workpieces comply with all metrics, twelve workpieces fail on at least one metric, and the workpiece No. 4 has missing data.

The **Alicona** dataset measures the surface roughness of the workpiece after machining. The roughness is measured by 15 metrics, among which Ra is the most important according to the Challenge Owner.

2.4 Data quality issues

The first limitation of the dataset is the fact that there are only 16 parts, and that each of these parts has thousands of datapoints associated with them.

Moreover, as it is common in industry, these datasets have missing data. In particular:

- Spike dataset has no information regarding parts 03, 07, 08, 10, and 16.
- Tooling dataset has no information about piece 03. Also, part 07 is missing the process 040 and part 09 has two files for process 020.

3 Data exploration and visualisation

We first performed data exploration. After a systematic study of various datasets, we made two important discoveries.

3.1 Influence of forging temperature regime

The Challenge Owner told us that the processing conditions for all 16 workpieces were all the same except for the temperature. Our exploration revealed that this temperature difference entailed some secondary differences.

The processing conditions for the workpieces forged under lower temperature (hereafter referred to as the cold group) showed more variety compared to their counterparts under higher temperature (hereafter referred to as the hot group).

For instance, the `Force[kN]` and `TMP_Ind_F [C]` variables show that the hot group all went through nearly identical working conditions whereas the processing of the cold group saw interesting events at different moments and also lasted for different durations (Figure 2 and 3).

This indicates that the manufacturer experimented with different processing techniques within the cold group.

Figure 2: Measurements of the `TMP_Ind_F [C]` variable over the cold and hot group. The X-axis indicates the time.

3.2 Tool wearing decreases sequentially

Our exploration of the wearing data in the tooling dataset revealed that the tooling process followed a coarse-to-fine pattern. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that subprocesses earlier in the machining process cause larger amounts of gross wear, possibly correlated with larger interventions by the tool.

We plotted the wearing (Y-axis) against the various subprocesses (X-axis) in the tooling stage (Figure 4). Assuming that the latter subprocesses have a larger index than the earlier ones, we can deduce that the wearing decreases gradually.

4 Statistical modelling

It is reasonable to assume that the sensor readings taken during the forging and machining process will reflect the major factors which determine how likely a part is to be finally rejected; however, the precise dynamics at play are not yet entirely clear. Since determining the precise causes through either extensive experimentation or physical simulation

Figure 3: Measurements of the Force [kN] variable over the cold and hot group. The X-axis indicates the time.

would be both time-consuming and resource-intensive, the approach of the statistical sub-group was to use models to understand the relationship of sensor data variables to the process outcome quality measures, and produce a system capable of accurately inferring the outcome from new sets of input data.

We broke down the tasks into two sub-tasks:

1. we extracted relevant features including statistical and temporal correlations from time-series sensor data collected during the forging and machining processes.
2. we leveraged Alicona roughness measures and CMM workpiece dimension data to build a single unified output measure of quality.

Finally, we combined these two sub-tasks together by relating the workpiece quality to the time series features in order to identify the factors influencing the workpiece quality.

Figure 4: Wearing in each subprocess. The X-axis indicates the ID of the subprocess following the sequential order, and the Y-axis is the wearing.

4.1 Feature extraction

4.1.1 Forging data

We observed a common pattern in all time series in the forging data, namely that the majority of the time, the time series have low values. Only at some specific moments does the time series peak, e.g. there is relatively high variance in the reading. We hypothesised that only the extreme values are of interest, and the remaining low values correspond to sensor noise. Therefore, we thresholded each time series feature, replacing each by its absolute maximum as the new (scalar) feature.

4.1.2 Machining data

Since the machining data is composed of the spike, edge, and tooling datasets, we started by aggregating these into a single dataset. The major difficulty in this step is the different sample frequency of the spike and edge dataset. The former is sampled every 0.4ms (2.5kHz), and the latter every 3ms (333Hz). We opted to interpolate and down-sample the spike dataset to align it with the edge dataset.

Columns with no variance have also been removed as they don't add any value to the data, as listed in Table 1.

Feature Name	
CycleCYCLE	PowerPOWER_4
CurrentCURRENT_1	PowerPOWER_6
CurrentCURRENT_2	PowerPOWER_15
CurrentCURRENT_3	PowerPOWER_7
CurrentCURRENT_4	PowerPOWER_8
CurrentCURRENT_6	LoadLOAD_1
CurrentCURRENT_7	LoadLOAD_2
CurrentCURRENT_8	LoadLOAD_3
CurrentCURRENT_15	LoadLOAD_6
PowerPOWER_1	LoadLOAD_7
PowerPOWER_2	LoadLOAD_8
PowerPOWER_3	GCode

Table 1: List of columns removed from machining sensor data.

At this stage, the dataset contains millions of rows and 55 columns. So, we decided to reduce the dimensionality using PCA. However, the multiplication wasn't feasible given the the size of the matrices and current memory limitations. This approach could be further explored if access to enough memory and/or different technical methods were employed.

Given we have an $n \ll p$ problem - high-dimensional time series data with 52 variables, and only sixteen instances - some feature extraction and selection methods will be needed to select explanatory variables in modelling. Firstly we used contextual information provided by AMRC to

select a subset of the features: ‘Tension’, ‘Torsion’, ‘Bending moment X’, ‘Bending moment Y’ from the Spike data; ‘Torque 1’, ‘Torque FeedForward’ and ‘Actual Axis Position ENC POS 1’ from the Edge data; and ‘Wear difference’ describing the wear of the machining part from the Tooling data”.

Since it is difficult to work on time series directly, we used the `tsfel` package [1] to extract features from each variable. This package is designed for bulk feature extraction from time series data. It offers three types of features: statistical, temporal, and spectral. Due to the high computational cost, we did not use the spectral features. After this step, we got a total of 36 features, such as absolute energy, area under the curve (AUC), and auto-correlation. That is, given $X_{t;i,j,k}$, where t indexes time, i indexes the variable/metric, j indexes the part and k indexes the process, we extract features $\hat{X}_{i,j,k}$.

Having now obtained features for each time series, we need to select a subset of these new features $\hat{X}_{i,j,k}$ to use in modelling. We do this by assessing the variance $Var(\hat{X}_{i,j,k})$ of each of the features across the parts, that is with fixed i and k with varying j . The idea is that those with higher variance are capturing the differences between the parts.

Doing this across all measures we conclude that some interesting features are ‘Tension_Centroid’, ‘Torsion_Mean diff’, ‘Bending moment X_Slope’, ‘Bending moment Y_Slope’

4.2 Quality metrics

Multiple datasets describe the quality of the workpiece. During the DSG, we studied only the geometric and roughness aspect of the workpiece due to time constraints.

There are 13 geometric features for each piece with corresponding tolerance measures, see Table 2.

Additionally, there is the surface roughness (R_a) to be considered. In terms of surface roughness, anything that is less than or equal to 1.6 is considered to have ‘passed’ - i.e. the part will not be rejected as flawed. Values for each machining run are shown in Figure 5. The list of metrics and abbreviations are as follows:

Feature Name	NomValue	Tolerance
OD1 Diameter	44	0.25
OD2 Diameter	44	0.25
OD3 Diameter	44	0.25
ID1 Diameter	39	0.25
ID2 Diameter	39	0.25
ID3 Diameter	39	0.25
H1 Diameter	8	0.25
H2 Diameter	8	0.25
H3 Diameter	8	0.25
H4 Diameter	8	0.25
H5 Diameter	8	0.25
S1 Slot Width	13	0.5
S2 Slot Width	13	0.5

Table 2: Geometric quality measures with tolerances.

- Ra: Average roughness of profile
- Rq: Root-Mean-Square roughness of profile
- Rt: Maximum peak to valley height of roughness profile
- Rz: Mean peak to valley height of roughness profile
- Rmax: Maximum peak to valley height of roughness profile within a sampling length
- Rp: Maximum peak height of roughness profile
- Rv: Maximum valley height of roughness profile
- Rc: Mean height of profile irregularities of roughness profile
- Rsm: Mean spacing of profile irregularities of roughness profile
- Rsk: Skewness of roughness profile
- Rku: Kurtosis of roughness profile
- Rdq: Root-Mean-Square slope of roughness profile
- Rt/Rz: Extreme Scratch/Peak value of roughness profile

The idea is to construct some 'goodness of fit' measure (GOF) for these measurements and surface roughness to be compared to target values. Although all measurements within the tolerance are permissible, measurements closer to the target value are considered better fit. By defining a 'goodness of fit' measure, we can translate this binary

Figure 5: Values of all 16 machining runs across 13 roughness metrics.

classification problem (pass or fail) into a regression problem. Since the regression problem incorporates more information than its classification counterpart, we can create more informative models.

Accommodating the fact that the challenge owners communicated to us that the R_a was the most important measure for them, we considered constructing two measures. One for the geometric features fit, and the other for the R_a measure. After producing those measures, we can calculate a weighted score, giving more weight to the R_a measure and less weight to the geometric measure.

4.2.1 Geometric profile

For the geometric measures, we followed the principle that having more material left is better than having less. For instance, if a perfect workpiece has a length of 100mm, then a workpiece with 101mm is better than one with 99mm, although both are acceptable. The former can be reworked to further approach the 100mm target, whereas the latter does not have this potential. In our parlance, 101mm is better fit than 99mm, although they are equally close to 100 mm. From this reasoning, we can model the

fitness function with the density function of a right skew normal distribution.

The above modelling works only for metrics such as length, width, outer diameter. For metrics such as inner diameter, the situation is the opposite. A hole with a diameter of 9mm is better than one with 11mm when the target value is 10mm. The former can be reworked to further increase the diameter, whereas the latter does not have this potential. Although the underlying principle stays the same, we now should use the density function of a left skew normal distribution to model the fitness function.

Figure 6: A right skewed goodness of fit function.

Given all the information above, we proceeded as follows. Each of the nominal values and tolerances were used to fit a skewed normal distribution. Particle swarm optimisation was used to optimise the location, scale and shape parameters of the skewed normal distribution, minimising the distance between the mode of the distribution and the nominal value. Additionally, we fit it to the (0.1, 0.5, 0.9) quantiles, calculating the values at (Nominal - Tolerance, Nominal - $\frac{1}{2}$ Tolerance, Nominal + $\frac{1}{2}$ Tolerance) for left skewed distributions and (Nominal -

Figure 7: A left skewed goodness of fit function.

$\frac{1}{2}$ Tolerance, Nominal + $\frac{1}{2}$ Tolerance, Nominal +Tolerance) for right skewed distributions.

After the distributions are fitted, we can calculate the density value that corresponds to each 'observation' or measurement (density $d(x)$). In Figures 6 and 7, the $d(43.8) < d(44.2)$ for the right skewed distribution. However, for the left skewed distribution we have $d(38.75) > d(39.25)$. Additionally, we perform normalisation for each of those measures by dividing the $d(x)$ by the value at the mode of the distribution, scaling it to $[0, 1]$

Assuming independence of the measurements of the workpiece, we can add each individual GOF value for each of the features. We will divide that value by the number of features for normalisation.

4.2.2 Roughness profile

For the surface roughness R_a , all the measurements less than or equal to 1.6 are considered a 'pass', and everything above it is a 'failure'. In view of the fact that there might be different levels of failure, we considered the

following distribution:

$$\Gamma_{R_a}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq 1.6 \\ \frac{1}{10}\Gamma(x - 1.6; \alpha, \beta) & \text{if } x > 1.6, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\Gamma(x; \alpha, \beta)$ is a gamma distribution and $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 10$ are the shape and rate parameters of the gamma distribution (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Gamma goodness of fit function. The red vertical line corresponds to the tolerated value.

4.2.3 Total goodness of fit

This setup guarantees that the 'perfect' performance will receive a GOF_{geom} of 1 for the geometric measurement and a GOF_{R_a} of 1 for the R_a . However, keeping in mind that the R_a measure is more important than the geometric, we can do a weighted average

$GOF_{total} = w_1 \cdot GOF_{geom} + w_2 \cdot GOF_{Ra}$, where $w_1 + w_2 = 1$. Giving a higher weight w_2 to the GOF_{Ra} measure will prioritise satisfying that condition. The closer the GOF_{total} measure is to 1, the better the performance.

However, there is a drawback to using a weighted average when both measurements have to be within a threshold. In that case, a mildly poor measure can be covered by another exceptionally good measure. For example, when a workpiece is rejected as long as one of the measures is subpar.

In general, depending on the ultimate goal, different measures have benefits and drawbacks. Figure 9 shows two plots for a weighted average measure and a $\min(\text{GOF})$. The weighted average was calculated with $w_1 = 0.2$ and $w_2 = 0.8$.

4.3 Model Inference Results

In the first instance, we apply an XGBoost regression model [2] with the features discussed in the previous sections, using the total goodness of fit as a target for inference. We then calculate the SHAP values [6, 5] from the model to see which features are most important in predicting our quality metric. As many of the features are highly correlated and the data collection process in manufacturing is prone to missing data (e.g., human error, sensor failure), we picked XGBoost to counter these shortcomings. The usage of decision trees within XGBoost makes the model less affected by multicollinearity. Furthermore, the model can handle missing features which yields a model that is better suited for real-life usage.

The SHAP values, as shown in Figure 10 for the overall model and Figure 11 for a single workpiece, of our model indicate that a handful of parameters are key to the quality of the workpiece.

Despite the low number of samples, our model performs well in predicting the quality of workpieces. As early detection of potentially unfit workpieces is of economic interest, we also tried using the model with only the forging data. The model trained on forging data alone is equally informative (Figure 12). The corresponding SHAP value is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 9: The total goodness of fit for all workpieces. The X-axis is the number of the workpiece, and the Y-axis is the goodness of fit of the workpiece. Top: The total goodness of fit is a weighted average of GOF_{geom} and GOF_{Ra} . Bottom: The total goodness of fit is the minimum of GOF_{geom} and GOF_{Ra} .

Figure 10: SHAP values for quality prediction model. The SHAP values for all 16 workpieces and impactful variables are shown.

Figure 11: SHAP values for a single workpiece.

Figure 12: Estimated goodness of fit vs. true goodness of fit. Top: Using both the forging and machining data. Bottom: Using the forging data only.

Figure 13: Forging data model SHAP values.

5 Data augmentation

Our aim was to generate synthetic data that resembles the original data. The workflow for data augmentation is summarised in Figure 14. We used the Synthetic Data Vault (SDV) package [7] to build the baseline and then propose our own method for data augmentation (on Forging data only).

Figure 14: Our workflow for data augmentation.

Prior to performing any analysis, we perform data pre-processing. Specifically, we consider only forging feature variables that contain at least 10 unique values for all runs under the assumption that the remaining variables can be treated as constant. Therefore we managed to reduce the number of features from 101 down to 74.

5.1 Dimensionality reduction with PCA

Each forging feature comprises a time-series vector of 61,001 values, which makes the data augmentation process very computationally intensive. Prior to applying data augmentation algorithms, we therefore perform dimension reduction using principal component analysis (PCA).

For each forging variable, we aggregated all runs together into an $l \times n$ matrix F , where n and l correspond to the number of runs available ($n = 16$) and time-steps ($l = 61,001$). The singular values decomposition for F can be written as

$$F = U\Sigma V^T.$$

We specify the principal component basis $\Gamma = (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_{n-1})$, which are the first $n - 1$ columns of V and vector γ_i has length l . We choose only the first q basis vectors stored in the truncated basis matrix $\Gamma_q = (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_q)$ that explain at least 90% of total variance. From Figure 15, we can observe that for most of the forging features the first two basis vectors are sufficient to explain at least 90% of the total variance in the data. Since we are considering all forging features at the same time, we took the maximum required explanatory regime and retain 13 basis vectors.

In Figure 16, we consider as an example dimensionality reduction for the `power` feature time-series. Only two principal components are required to explain at least 90% of total variance in power data when we are considering all 16 runs. We can clearly see the separation between cold and hot forging from our plot with principal component coefficients.

5.2 SDV library

The initial baseline process for performing data augmentation made use of the Synthetic Data Vault (SDV) library, a piece of Python software that enables generation of new data through multiple methods, including classical statistical manipulation (e.g. copula) and deep learning. The following generation methods were implemented using this tool.

Probabilistic AutoRegressive (PAR) allows learning multivariate time series data to generate new synthetic data that has the same format and

Figure 15: The minimum of number of principal components required to explain at least 90% of total variance for each forging variable considered.

Figure 16: *Panel a*: Power time-series obtained under cold forging (in blue) and hot forging (in red). *Panel b*: Power time-series obtained under cold forging. *Panel c*: Power time-series obtained under hot forging. *Panel d*: The coefficients from the first two PCA (PC1 and PC2) obtained after dimension reduction for power time-series.

properties as the learned one. But, the PAR is not able to compute synthetic data for big time series (over 60,000 time steps) in a reasonable time.

Tableau Variational AutoEncoder (TVAE) and Conditional Tableau Generative Adversarial Network (CTGAN) view the data as a single tabular data with heterogeneous features (variables), which is consistent with the forging data. But, they may not be able to manage the time series properties.

We tried to learn from all data (16 workpieces) and learn from the hot and the cold group respectively, and evaluate them by the default function, which synthesises a quality metric from the similarity in per-column distribution and pair-wise correlations between the original and generated

datasets in the range $[0, 1]$. The higher the score, the more similar the sets are assumed to be. Both datasets scored similarly on this measure, with cold group scoring 0.659 with the hot group achieving a slightly higher result at 0.684. A sample of similarity measures for individual columns can be seen in Figure 17.

5.3 MAE method

Masked AutoEncoder(MAE) is a self-supervised learner [4]. In this paper, the researchers randomly masked patches of the original images and input the unmasked patches into the encoder, and predicted the masked patches to reconstruct the image by decoder. Their encoder and decoder are ViTs [3] based on a Transformer architecture. For our project, the dataset is tabular data, and we treat each data point as a pixel. At the same time, due to limited computation resource and constrained library, we decide to use three dense layers as the encoder, and three dense layers as the decoder.

5.3.1 Model Architecture

Our approach begins by using the method introduced in Section 5.1 to temporally compress the original time series data. This is done so that it can be consumed by our simple auto-encoder model. Some preprocessing (more information in Section 5.3.2) is applied to the compressed time series “image”. The processed images have random patches masked out (replaced with zeros). The masked images are fed into the model, which predicts complete compressed images, which are then compared to the original compressed image via mean square error (MSE).

Once the model is fully trained, we generate new synthetic time series data by taking the output of the model and projecting it back out into a full length time series (Figure 18).

5.3.2 Data preprocessing

Normalisation The original distribution of values in the time-compressed PCA “image” had quite a wide spread, with some

Figure 17: SDV results: Each row corresponds to one of the forging variable considered. Each column corresponds to the augmentation with all runs, cold forging runs and hot forging runs respectively. The original time-series data are in black, whereas the synthetic runs (10 runs) are in green.

Figure 18: Architecture of our network.

values being much higher than the others. We anticipated that this would cause problems for our model (e.g., getting stuck in local minima). We therefore calculated a normalised image I_n according to:

$$I_n = \frac{I - C_{min}}{C_{max} - C_{min}}$$

where I is the input image tensor, C_{min} is the tensor containing the minimum values of I 's columns, repeated in the y dimension. C_{max} is a similar tensor for I 's maximum values.

Normalisation is needed for the model to function effectively, but the output of the model needs to be de-normalised so that the original time series can be reconstructed. For this, we simply apply the inverse of the above operation to get the de-normalised image I_d :

$$I_d = C_{min} + I_n * (C_{max} - C_{min})$$

Note: Here, $*$ is the element-wise operator and does not compute the matrix product.

Masking The objective of masking the input images is to create a large set of training images for our auto-encoder to learn from in an unsupervised fashion. We iterate over 14 real images and for each one, apply our masking algorithm N times to create a batch of N training examples (Figure 19) The original image is then used as the ground truth

for each masked image in the batch. Overall, the model sees $14N$ training examples per epoch, where N is a hyper-parameter that was set to 16 in our case.

Figure 19: An example of masking.

5.3.3 Results

We applied our method on some of the forging variables and obtain results in Figure 20.

Figure 20: MAE results: Each column corresponds to one of the forging variable considered. The original time-series data are in black, whereas the synthetic runs (10 runs) are in green.

6 Future work and research avenues

In terms of specific recommendations for the current dataset, inconsistencies in the sample rate for specific sensors used during the

machining process (e.g. the spike and edge readings) required a significant loss of resolution during integration due to down-sampling. Ensuring that all readings are available at the same sample rate, and better consistency by eliminating missing values would inevitably have positive feedback effects on modelling performance.

Our statistical modelling results suggest that a handful of forging process data points are sufficient to estimate workpiece quality. This would enable significant savings in practice by avoiding further machining with a high likelihood of quality issues. Further possible research directions include the implementation of synthetic data to improve model performance as well as additional data gathering with case studies in practice.

We have tried two approaches to data augmentation: one out-of-the-box Python module and another custom-built model. Our data augmentation results suggest that more data from the “Hot” condition are needed.

7 Team members

Team members:

Bing Wang is a PhD candidate in informatics and system science at the Informatics Research Center, Henley Business School, University of Reading. His research interests are Natural Language Processing, Machine Learning and Graph Machine Learning. He has been working as a data scientist at Royal Berkshire NHS Foundation Trust since December 2019 during his PhD. His contribution to the data study group is data exploration and preprocessing and statistical modeling.

Daria Semochkina is a Research Fellow, S3RI, University of Southampton. They contributed to the statistical modelling aspect of the challenge.

Guowei Huang is a first year PhD student at Alliance Manchester Business School, University of Manchester. Guowei’s research focuses on applying machine learning and Natural Language process into business. Guowei was involved in analysis the dataset and developing the Mask Autoencoder Model for data argumentation.

Kavi Jayathunge is a PhD Student at Bournemouth University conducting research in Computer Vision, specifically an unsupervised approach to categorising human emotions from audiovisual input.

Kieran Baker is a final year PhD Statistics student at King's College London studying quantitative measures and modelling of Parkinson's Disease.

Linglong Qian is a PhD student in Biostatistics and Health Informatics (BHI) at King's College London.

Mercedeh Rezaei is a PhD Student at Queen Mary University, studying multi-stage techniques for ECG and heart arrhythmia detection and classification using Machine Learning.

Mohamad Reza Shahabian Alashti is a PhD candidate in the University of Hertfordshire in Computer Science.

Stefan Schoepf is a PhD student in the Supply Chain AI Lab at the University of Cambridge. His research focuses on multi-agent reinforcement learning for supply chain optimization.

Tereso del Rio is a PhD student at Coventry University. He uses Machine Learning to speed up Computer Algebra procedures. He contributed to data visualization, looking for anomalies and feature extraction.

Victoria Volodina is a Research Fellow at University College London on a collaborative project in mathematics, engineering and AI, CHIMERA, one of four national hubs for mathematics and healthcare.

Wenjie Zheng was the Principal Investigator (PI) for this project.

Challenge Owners:

Jon Stammers is the Senior Theme Lead for Data, Connectivity and AI at the University of Sheffield AMRC. He joined the AMRC in 2013 working in the Process Monitoring and Control team, becoming a Technical Fellow in 2017. He has lectured at the AMRC Training Centre, assisting with the design of the Bachelors in Manufacturing (BMan) course.

Lindsay Lee is a Technical Fellow for Data Science at AMRC. She has 15 years' experience using statistics and machine learning to solve

domain-specific problems in manufacturing and climate science. She has articles in *Nature*, *The Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* and the *RSS Significance Magazine* demonstrating the power of statistics for domain understanding. She has done public lectures for the Royal Statistical Society and the Royal Meteorology Society on the use of statistics for uncertainty quantification.

References

- [1] Marília Barandas et al. “TSFEL: Time series feature extraction library”. In: *SoftwareX* 11 (2020), p. 100456.
- [2] Tianqi Chen and Carlos Guestrin. “Xgboost: A scalable tree boosting system”. In: *Proceedings of the 22nd acm sigkdd international conference on knowledge discovery and data mining*. 2016, pp. 785–794.
- [3] Alexey Dosovitskiy et al. “An Image is Worth 16x16 Words: Transformers for Image Recognition at Scale”. In: *International Conference on Learning Representations*. 2021. URL: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=YicbFdNTTy>.
- [4] Kaiming He et al. “Masked autoencoders are scalable vision learners”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2022, pp. 16000–16009.
- [5] Scott M Lundberg, Gabriel G Erion, and Su-In Lee. “Consistent individualized feature attribution for tree ensembles”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.03888* (2018).
- [6] Scott M Lundberg and Su-In Lee. “A Unified Approach to Interpreting Model Predictions”. In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*. Ed. by I. Guyon et al. Vol. 30. Curran Associates, Inc., 2017. URL: <https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2017/file/8a20a8621978632d76c43dfd28b67767-Paper.pdf>.
- [7] N. Patki, R. Wedge, and K. Veeramachaneni. “The Synthetic Data Vault”. In: *2016 IEEE International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*. Oct. 2016, pp. 399–410. DOI: 10.1109/DSAA.2016.49.

- [8] Julian Senoner, Torbjørn Netland, and Stefan Feuerriegel. “Using explainable artificial intelligence to improve process quality: Evidence from semiconductor manufacturing”. In: *Management Science* 68.8 (2022), pp. 5704–5723.

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

**turing.ac.uk
@turinginst**